

Kinetics of Reaction of Triethylammonium Carboxylates with α -Halogenocarbonyl Compounds in Organic Solvents. Part-II. Reaction of *trans*-Cinnamates with Phenacyl Bromide in Acetone^{1†}

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The second order rate constants (k_2) for the reaction of phenacyl bromide with triethylammonium *para*-substituted *trans*-cinnamates in acetone have been determined at 303, 305 and 313 K and the activation parameters evaluated. The effect of addition of water on the rate constant is rationalised. Electron-releasing groups retard the reaction while electron-withdrawing groups facilitate it. The reversal of the order of the substituent effects has been rationalised. Linear regression analysis of $\log k_2$ with Hammett σ gave a ρ value of +0.19 with $r = 0.997$.

THE reactivity of α -halogenoketones towards nucleophilic reagents has been the subject of several investigations. Their reactivities have been ascribed to a polar effect in which the electron-attracting carbonyl group induces an electron deficient centre at the carbon atom holding the halogen atom², thereby facilitating the approach of a nucleophile towards this carbon. Carboxylate anions are found to be potential nucleophiles in this reaction. Carboxylic acids undergo esterification with alkyl halides or α -halogenocarbonyl compounds in the presence of basic amines³⁻⁵ in aprotic solvents. The acids form complexes, triethylammonium carboxylates with the amine, and these are the active nucleophiles in the esterification reaction. The structure and spectral characteristics of these complexes have been extensively studied⁶⁻¹² and it has been concluded that these complexes exist as ion-pairs in aprotic solvents. The detailed structural features of the ion-pair depend upon the nature of the solvent employed. The reaction of alkyl halides or phenacyl halides with triethylamine-carboxylic acid complexes is not exploited much for kinetic study, although the kinetics of the reactions of phenacyl bromide with substituted benzoates¹³⁻¹⁴, naphthoates¹⁵, and cinnamates¹⁶ in 90% (or 85%) (v/v) acetone-water mixtures are reported. Recently, Pillay *et al.*¹ investigated the kinetics of reactions of phenacyl bromide with *para*-substituted-benzoic acids and phenoxyacetic acids in the presence of triethylamine in acetone and concluded that the active nucleophile is a hydrogen-bonded ion-pair. We report here our investigations on the kinetics of the S_N2 reactions of phenacyl bromide with *para*-substituted-cinnamic acids in the presence of triethylamine.

Experimental

Technical grade cinnamic acid and hydrocinnamic acid were recrystallised from water until the m.p. remained constant after subsequent crystallisations and agreed with the literature values¹⁷. *p*-Methyl-¹⁷, *p*-methoxy-¹⁸, *p*-nitro-¹⁸, *p*-chloro-¹⁸, *p*-bromo-¹⁸, *p*-iodo-¹⁹ and *p*-cyano-cinnamic acids²⁰ were prepared by the best available procedure. Acetone (AnalaR) was purified by following the method of Sachs²¹. Phenacyl bromide was prepared²² by the bromination of acetophenone. The kinetic method has been described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

Carboxylic acids undergo esterification with phenacyl bromide readily in the presence of triethylamine²³. This acceleration in activity can be attributed to the coordination of triethylammonium ion with carboxylate ion by hydrogen bonding². The triethylammonium group acts as the source of electrons which may act via the H-bond, to transfer negative charge to the organic part of the complex, hence generating a highly reactive cinnamate anion.

The order of reactivities of triethylammonium hydrocinnamate, benzoate, acetate, cinnamate and phenylacetate in acetone is hydrocinnamate < acetate < cinnamate < phenylacetate < benzoate as given in Table 1. This order is just the reverse of the basicity order of the anion as determined from the pK_a values of the corresponding acids. However, in aqueous acetone, the order of reactivities of sodium carboxylates corresponds to the

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TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANT VALUES FOR TRIETHYLAMMONIUM SALTS OF ORGANIC ACIDS IN ACETONE AND pK_a VALUES

Acid	k_2^* $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	pK_a
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$	0.70	4.37 ^b
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$	0.987	4.76 ^a
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOOH}$	1.992	4.44 ^b
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$	1.310	4.31 ^a
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$	1.560	4.20 ^a

*At 303 K.

^aRef. 24 ^bRef. 25.

basicity order²⁴. Hence, under the present reaction conditions, the active species is different from that in aqueous acetone. Our studies on triethylammonium benzoate has proved that the amine-acid complex exists only as a hydrogen bonded ion-pair in acetone and there is no evidence for the existence of free benzoate or free trimethylammonium cation¹. On this basis, we assume that cinnamic acid-triethylamine complex also exists as a hydrogen bonded ion-pair. The rate of reaction of triethylammonium cinnamate ($k_2 = 14.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and triethylammonium benzoate¹ ($k_2 = 15.57 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) in dry acetone were comparable indicating similar type of active species in both the nucleophilic reactions. Hence, the mechanism of the reaction is also similar to that of benzoate¹.

Solvent effects: The kinetics of the reaction of triethylammonium cinnamate with phenacyl bromide at 308 K were carried out in acetone and aqueous acetone and the data are presented in Table 2. In

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF WATER ON RATE OF REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE WITH TRIETHYLAMMONIUM *trans*-CINNAMATE

Sl no.	% water in aqueous acetone	Mole fraction of water	k $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\log k_2$
1.	0	—	14.92	—
2.	5	0.176	9.18	-2.037 2
3.	10	0.312	6.48	-2.188 4
4.	15	0.418	5.02	-2.299 3
5.	20	0.505	3.56	-2.448 0
6.	25	0.576	2.46	-2.609 0
7.	30	0.636	2.22	-2.653 6
8.	35	0.687	1.60	-2.795 9
9.	40	0.731	1.24	2.920 8

*At 308 K.

the binary solvent, aqueous acetone, the magnitude of decrease in rate is very significant in the initial increment of water composition and becomes less significant as the composition of water is increased. The rate constant attains a steady value at the higher concentration of water (Fig. 1). The rate constant is very much affected when the reaction medium is changed from acetone to aqueous 5% acetone. This considerable change may be due to the decomposition of the hydrogen bonded complex

to a solvent-separated ion-pair or to hydrated cinnamate ion and triethylammonium ion. Further decrease in rate constant with increasing ionising power of the solvent can be accounted on the basis of Hughes-Ingold theory^{27,28}. In the S_N2 reaction between free (in high aqueous composition) cinnamate and phenacyl bromide the nucleophile is more polar than the transition state. Therefore, the reactant is more stabilised with increasing ionising power of the medium.

 Fig. 1. Plot of k_2 vs % water in acetone.

Substituent effects: The rate constant for triethylammonium *para*-substituted-cinnamates have been determined at 303, 308 and 313 K in plain acetone and are presented in Table 3. A comparison of the rate constant shows that electron-releasing substituents act as retarders, while halogens and electron-withdrawing substituents act as accelerators for the reaction. However, the reactivity order shown in Table 3 is different from the

 TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE WITH *para*-SUBSTITUTED-*trans*-CINNAMIC ACIDS IN PRESENCE OF TRIETHYLAMINE IN ACETONE

Sl. no.	Substituent	$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		303 K	308 K	313 K		
1.	4-NH ₂	0.305	0.373	0.585	38.78	166.5
2.	4-OCH ₃	0.871	1.14	1.54	39.24	156.1
3.	4-CH ₃	0.928	1.19	1.57	38.58	158.2
4.	4-H	0.992	1.40	1.70	40.08	151.8
5.	4-NO ₂	1.47	1.81	2.57	42.00	143.5
6.	4-CN	—	1.71	—	—	—
7.	4-Cl	1.06	1.48	1.83	46.44	130.1
8.	4-Br	1.02	1.44	1.79	43.93	138.5
9.	4-I	1.01	1.42	1.78	43.10	143.1

expected order based on the kinetic studies of the reaction of sodium cinnamates¹⁰, *i.e.* $p\text{-OMe} > p\text{-Me} > \text{H} > p\text{-Br} > p\text{-Cl} > p\text{-NO}_2$. This can be rationalised only when the thermodynamic parameters are analysed carefully.

Activation parameters for the reactions of phenacyl bromide with *para*-substituted-*trans*-cinnamate ions are presented in Table 3. The entropies

indicates the reduced effectiveness of π -electron transmission in cinnamic acid relative to benzoic acid.

TABLE 4—ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION FOR REACTION OF SOME CARBOXYLATES WITH PHENACYL BROMIDE

Sl. no	Nucleophile	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	References
1	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CHCOO ⁻ HN ⁺ (Et) ₃ ^a	151.9 ^o	Present work
2	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CHCOO ⁻ Na ⁺ ^b	80.2 ^d	16
3	C ₆ H ₅ COO ⁻ HN ⁺ (Et) ₃ ^a	126.8 ^o	1
4	C ₆ H ₅ COO ⁻ Na ⁺ ^b	15.9 ^f	14
5	1-C ₁₀ H ₇ COO ⁻ Na ⁺ ^b	90.0 ^o	15
6	2-C ₁₀ H ₇ COO ⁻ Na ⁺ ^b	5.5 ^h	26
7	C ₆ H ₅ OCH ₂ COO ⁻ HN ⁺ (Et) ₃ ^a	162.3 ^o	1

^aAcetone. ^bAqueous 90% acetone. ^oPresent work.
^dRef. 16. ^eRef. 1. ^fRef. 14. ^gRef. 15. ^hRef. 26.

of activation are negative in all cases as expected for bimolecular reactions and the values are high. A greater crowding in the transition state is mainly responsible for rigid transition state leading to considerable decrease in entropy. The ΔS^\ddagger values for the reactions of sodium benzoate, sodium naphthoate, sodium cinnamate are compared with those of triethylammonium benzoate, phenoxyacetate and *trans*-cinnamate in Table 4. To account for the considerable negative entropy of activation a cyclic transition state of the type (I) has been visualised for the reaction between triethylammonium cinnamate and phenacyl bromide, as in the case of benzoate.

The $\log k_2$ values have been fitted to the Hammett equation by the least-squares analysis. Hammett ρ values²⁹⁻³¹ are used for correlation. The correlation is found to be good ($r=0.997$) and value of ρ is $+0.19$. The magnitude of ρ indicates that this series shows less sensitivity to substituent changes than the ionisation of substituted-benzoic acids. The ratio of ρ/ρ_0 (ρ_0 is that of benzoic acid series which is equal to $+0.37$) is known as the attenuation ratio (π) and it was found to be 0.51 . This was thought as a measure of the transmission of polar effect through the sidechain³². This result

The values of $\log k_2$ for the various substituted-cinnamic acids in this reaction series have been evaluated and a plot of $\log k_{2(\text{obs})}$ vs $\log k_{2(\text{calc})}$ gives points, most of which fall in the 45° line indicating that the estimation and observation are in good agreement.

Isokinetic relation.hip: A linear relationship between the entropy and enthalpy of activation has been found. This proves that the same mechanism operates in this series as it is required in order to correctly apply LFER. In the isokinetic plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger , the data points were subjected to least-squares analysis and the correlation coefficient (r) was found to be 0.990. The least-squares values for the intercept, ΔH^\ddagger_0 and the slope, β (isokinetic temperature) were obtained as 77.3 kJ mol⁻¹ and 242 K, respectively. The isokinetic temperature was also computed by plotting $\log k_2$ at 313 K against $\log k_2$ at 303 K. A linear plot was obtained which confirms the Exner equation^{33,34}. The values were subjected to least-squares analysis and the correlation coefficient r was found to be 0.990 and the value of β was calculated as 263 K. All the runs were carried out at 303, 308 and 313 K and so the reaction temperatures are always above the isokinetic temperature calculated by any one of the above two methods. This explains why the order of reactivities of the substituents observed is contrary to our expectation^{35,36}. The reverse effect is due to the fact that the reaction temperature is above the isokinetic temperature. The results of the kinetic study of the reaction of phenacyl bromide with benzoic acids and phenoxyacetic acids in the presence of triethylamine support this conclusion¹.

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